

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP6 – Outreach and Sustainability

D6.2 First version of value propositions for stakeholders

- Publishable version -

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	13 May 2019	First Draft
V1.1	10 June 2019	First full draft for review
V1.2	14 June 2019	Final Draft for formal review
V1.3	20 June 2019	Final Version for consortium review
V1.4	1 July 2019	Final Version after consortium review (minor changes)

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports on the methodology used and results obtained to create the first versions of value propositions (VP) for priority stakeholders. The three priority stakeholders agreed by the Consortium are small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), data sources and regulatory/HTA/payer agencies.

The methodology used followed a stepwise approach:

- Breakout brainstorming sessions at the project kick-off meeting, to identify the stakeholders, to define an initial list of key benefits per stakeholder, and other relevant aspects
- Configuration of VP teams (one per priority stakeholder)
- Creation of a first version of each VP document
- Review of the VP document and survey among VP team members to refine and rank importance of key benefits
- Full text version produced and reviewed

As a result, a stable first version of value propositions for SMEs, data sources and regulatory/HTA agencies was obtained and is included in this deliverable. These are considered living documents and will be refined during the project as needed. Next steps will entail producing VP documents for other key stakeholders.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable aims at describing the strategy developed within WP6 (Outreach and Sustainability) in order to develop Value Propositions for different types of project stakeholders.

Participants agreed early on in the project on a list of different, key stakeholders for EHDEN. A first group of stakeholders that ought to be prioritised and centre the work on the first Value Propositions was also identified, namely:

- SMEs- data mapping service and tool developers
- Data sources/Data custodians/National Health Data Networks
- Regulatory/Health Technology Assessment/Payer agencies

These VPs would be used by the teams in charge of outreaching to the different stakeholders as tools or guidelines to ensure a successful liaison with them.

2. METHODOLOGY

WP6 Outreach and Sustainability developed a process for the preparation of the Value Propositions, depicted in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. WP6 OUTREACH WORKFLOW

The process was based on WP leaders defining and prioritising stakeholders. This would serve as a basis for a stakeholder registry (see deliverable 6.1) where the different institutions that should be targeted for outreach activities could be classified. The registry would be fed by partners leveraging their networks of contacts and previous knowledge about institutions that should be reached out to for involvement in the project. In parallel, 'VP teams' would develop value propositions for each type of stakeholder. The resulting VP documents would be used by small 'outreach teams' to approach specific stakeholders. The process is

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completed by tracking interactions, evaluating the relative success of the strategy, and providing feedback that allows to change priorities, adjust the VPs and improve the registry, so that a learning process is enabled.

This strategy was presented and approved at the WP leads kick-off meeting (ExCom), held on the 23rd of November 2018 in Brussels. In this meeting an initial list of stakeholders, and three priority groups were identified:

- SMEs- data mapping service and tool developers
- Data sources/Data custodians/National Health Data Networks
- Regulatory/Health Technology Assessment/Payer agencies

The first two were natural choices due to first calls to be issued by EHDEN, addressed to SMEs and data sources. Regulatory and HTA/payer agencies were also deemed to be of critical importance due to their value as potential catalysts of the intended EHDEN ecosystem.

At the project Kick-off Meeting, held on the 15-16 January 2019 in Rotterdam, specific breakout sessions to tackle the work towards preparation of the Value Propositions were organised. Three breakout sessions were held, corresponding to three priority stakeholder types.

Each session was planned as a brainstorming, where the participants would freely discuss to identify key components of the value proposition:

- Objectives of outreach
- Key concepts for VP
- Relative importance of each key benefit
- Order and wording
- Format of interaction, target people, timeliness

Flipcharts were used to dynamically capture the ideas of the audience based on the scheme depicted in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. VALUE PROPOSITIONS BRAINSTORMING

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After the Kick-off meeting, three ‘VP teams’ were created to work separately on each of the VPs. A call for volunteers was done through the Forum, which triggered the VP teams for each priority group.

3. DEVELOPMENT OF FIRST VERSIONS OF THE VALUE PROPOSITIONS

On the basis of the brainstorming session and knowledge from previous projects and experiences, a first draft of the VP for each of the three priority stakeholder types was developed, summarising the key benefits and the other aspects mentioned. These first drafts were circulated within the corresponding VP teams for review, together with an online survey (Figure 3) aimed at allowing members to score the key benefits to give a measure of the relative importance of each.

FIGURE 3. ONLINE SURVEY FOR VP DEVELOPMENT

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The online survey included the list of key benefits as included in the first draft of the VP, and respondents were asked to score each of them. This proved to be useful to assess the relative importance of those key benefits, as well as to collect specific feedback on them. The full online survey for the three VPs is available in Annex 1.

Once completed surveys were received and a preliminary analysis was done, dedicated teleconferences were organised for each of the three teams to discuss in detail all points included in the draft Value Propositions, the feedback received and the results of the survey.

The outcome of the calls was used as consensus to develop the VPs further. Key benefits were re-arranged, refined and further developed. Results from the survey helped to reorder the key benefits according to the scoring received (see figures 4-6). The key benefits were developed into full text versions of each VP, suitable for direct use in communication materials and as guide for the outreach teams that will be contacting stakeholders.

The first full versions of the Value Propositions for the three groups have been made accessible to all partners using the internal project channels (Sharepoint and Forum) and are considered to be 'living documents' that will be continuously refined during the project lifetime according to the feedback received from partners using them and the degree of success observed in outreach activities.

FIGURE 4. MEAN SCORE FOR KEY BENEFITS FOR SMEs

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FIGURE 5. MEAN SCORE FOR KEY BENEFITS FOR DATA SOURCES

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FIGURE 6. MEAN SCORE FOR KEY BENEFITS FOR REGULATORY/HTA

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4. VALUE PROPOSITIONS

The resulting first version of the full text of the Value Propositions can be found in the next sections.

4.1. Value propositions for SMEs – data mapping service and tool developers

4.1.1. Objectives of outreach

- To raise awareness on the existing possibilities and support to map to OMOP-CDM, including **EHDEN grants, and the role of certified SMEs in service provision following grant awards.**
- To raise **awareness on EHDEN and its training and certification process, resources involved and output.**
- To get commitment to **participate in the EHDEN community.**
- To raise awareness on the role of real-world evidence in healthcare, how observational data are used to support industry, government, regulators, academia and health systems.
- To raise **awareness on the need for standardisation, increasing momentum across stakeholders and the role of the OMOP-CDM** for real-world evidence and related businesses.
- To raise awareness on the **emerging, potential markets** related to service provision around the OMOP CDM and OHDSI analytic tools (mapping services, tool development, customisation).

4.1.2. Key concepts for VP

Headline¹:

Option 1 - **“UNLEASH THE VALUE OF DATA IN A FAST-GROWING MARKET”**

Option 2 - **“NEW MARKETS FOR YOUR DATA SKILLS”**

Key benefits:

1. Expand existing market:
 - a. Expand the customer base: new customers, networking opportunities with e.g. big pharma companies interested in deploying and developing tools for data use, and a plethora of data sources willing to be mapped to OMOP CDM and asking for support (up to 100 million health records expected to be mapped to OMOP CDM in EHDEN)
 - b. Expand the range of services and products related to those already delivered – particularly for IT companies to expand to data sciences provider, opening doors to scientific endeavours beyond the technical realm
 - c. Geography: Potential worldwide markets, underpinned by OHDSI’s activities
2. New market opportunities related to development of new added value services in the ‘hot’ area of data sciences where no company occupies the entire space:
 - a. Health data interoperability: mapping to OMOP CDM
 - b. Infrastructure design and deployment, custom installs (e.g. especially fine-tuned tools, linking preferred data sources) for data exploitation for specific customers
 - c. Large-scale analysis of health data: analytics tool development and deployment
 - d. Provider of data analysis support for small to mid-size pharma, biotech, medical device companies that cannot afford to staff such expertise internally, or to other stakeholders having adopted the OMOP CDM

¹ This would be the ‘title’ of the VP, typically displayed in large font on a landing page

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- e. Enabler of high throughput studies by connecting data users and providers
 - f. Training on the use of OHDSI tools and observational analyses
 - g. Ongoing support and maintenance of connected data and provided solutions
3. Early adopters will gain competitive advantage on specialised skill set and leverage the certified status
 4. Possibility to contribute to a change of paradigm benefitting health of citizens
 5. Short-term income generation (grants) to offset the cost and risk of skill investment
 6. Free training and certification process
 7. Open source community distributes burden of development and offers many opportunities for product and service development on top of existing and future tools
 8. Thriving community facilitates hands-on training of new staff
 9. Synergic ecosystem facilitates exposure and brand recognition with academia, industry and other key stakeholders, helping improve market positioning

4.1.3. Relative importance of key concepts

Due to the specific characteristics of SMEs (limited personnel, cash-flow tensions), short term revenue may take priority over future promises of new markets and high market shares.

4.1.4. VP team members

The members for this VP team are:

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4.1.5. VP full text

The following text develops the key benefits in section 4.1.2 above. This will serve as guideline to develop argumentation for outreach teams contacting potentially interested SMEs, and as text that can be directly used for dissemination materials, web site, etc.

UNLEASH THE VALUE OF HEALTH DATA IN A FAST-GROWING MARKET

- **Expand your existing market**

If your company is already operating in the data science, health data interoperability, bioinformatics or medical informatics fields, EHDEN offers a gateway into multiple opportunities for growth.

- a. Expand your customer base

EHDEN will create an eco-system where a variety of stakeholders (hospitals, health data sources, pharmaceutical and related industries, authorities...) will be able to seamlessly network and collaborate. This will be an unmatched opportunity for your company to expand your customer

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base, including data users interested in deploying and developing tools, and a plethora of data sources willing to be mapped to the OMOP CDM asking for support. Up to 100 million European health records expected to be mapped to OMOP CDM thanks to EHDEN, underpinning a newly populated landscape for health data solutions.

b. Expand the range of services and products you can offer

EHDEN will allow your data skills to be taken to the next level. New products and services will flourish within the EHDEN eco-system thanks to an extraordinary improvement in our capacity to re-use health data. IT-centred companies will be able to expand their range of products and services to act as data sciences providers, opening doors to scientific endeavours beyond the technical realm.

c. Expand your geographical reach

EHDEN is a European project, so its scope includes hundreds of data users and providers scattered all over Europe. Additionally, EHDEN builds on and will be deeply connected with OHDSI, an international open community promoting the OMOP CDM, which is now widely adopted from the USA to South Korea. Participating in EHDEN opens the door for your company to be exposed to a growing worldwide market.

• **Contribute to the creation of emerging, new markets for data sciences**

Beyond established markets, there are huge opportunities arising derived from a brand new way of understanding and using health data. EHDEN aspires to facilitate the creation of new markets that support the needs of both data users and providers, a currently incipient field where your company could play a pivotal role:

a. Health data mapping to the OMOP CDM

EHDEN will foster and financially support mapping of European data sources to the OMOP CDM using certified small and medium enterprises. This will offer short-term opportunities for service provision. As a critical mass of mapped data sources is reached and reliance on interoperability standards increases, a 'snowball' effect will raise the need of many other data sources to also adopt the CDM, in what is likely to be an exponentially growing market.

b. Large-scale analytics tool development

The ultimate aim of EHDEN is to enable better, faster large-scale analysis of health data for different purposes. It relies on the vibrant OHDSI open source community, where tools are continuously developed and tested. Companies operating in this space will therefore have unique opportunities to further create, develop and deploy analytics tools for the variety of stakeholders that will co-exist within the EHDEN eco-system.

c. Data analysis services for small and medium biomedical companies

Beyond big pharma, the biomedical field is populated by numerous small and medium size pharma, biotech and medical device companies that cannot or do not want to staff data analysis expertise internally, for efficiency reasons. The same can apply to other public and private institutions. Companies with knowledge and experience in using the OMOP CDM will be able to benefit from these outsourcing opportunities to develop new services related to data analysis.

d. Infrastructure design and deployment

Data users will need to be connected to their preferred data sources, which will call for service providers that can design, develop and customise infrastructure solutions and fine-tune available tools for streamlining and optimising data use according to the needs of each customer.

e. Enabler of high throughput studies by bridging data users and providers

Beyond infrastructure, companies may also directly facilitate the undertaking of studies and other ways of using health data for a variety of purposes. This brokering role may be especially important in the future due to the growing requirement to carry out multi-centre international

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studies in a transparent way to ensure that the best evidence is used for decision making purposes.

f. Training on the use of OHDSI tools and observational analyses

Companies engaging with EHDEN will have unique access to specialised knowledge and hands-on training. This will allow to in turn train others on both technical and scientific aspects of the OMOP CDM and its application, from ETL to high-efficiency analytics.

g. Ongoing support and maintenance of connected data and provided solutions

The world changes fast. All new products and services developed in this emerging field, no matter how novel or revolutionary now, will need continuing support and maintenance. The potential of health data use will only grow with time. For small and medium enterprises, providing ongoing support may represent a stable revenue source that helps offset the risks of further research and investment in new products.

- **Early adopters will gain competitive advantage on specialised skill set**

In most of these emerging markets, there are currently no dominant players that cover all the potential services. Early adopters of the EHDEN training and certification mechanism will possess a competitive advantage and be uniquely placed to innovate and benefit from privileged market positioning. They will have early experience on deploying the CDM and its application in different contexts and use cases. This will enable long term growth strategies, focussing on relative strong areas and developing a solid customer base before the markets mature.

- **Possibility to contribute to a change of paradigm benefitting health of citizens**

EHDEN aims to be truly revolutionary in how the wealth of existing health data can be best used for the ultimate benefit of the patient – enabling better decision making by health professionals, better drugs being developed earlier, better understanding of disease processes... all of which will create positive feedback loops on our ability to generate, analyse and use data. Companies contributing to the eco-system will help develop such learning healthcare systems, for the benefit of all. Profit making is essential for any company, but nothing equals the feeling of having decisively contributed to a better world.

- **Short-term income generation to offset skill investment**

EHDEN will launch periodic calls for data sources that are interested in being mapped to the OMOP CDM. Data sources that are evaluated positively will receive funding in the form of a grant, and they will be able to use it to hire certified SMEs for mapping services. This will offer an opportunity for SMEs to generate revenue, but most importantly, to acquire experience in real-life scenarios all over Europe.

- **Free training and certification**

The best part – the EHDEN training and certification programme for SMEs is free of charge. Interested SMEs just need to apply to one of the periodic calls and commit to contribute to the development of the EHDEN eco-system. Applications will be evaluated by experts and successful SMEs will be invited to join the training programme and get certified. You will still have to of course invest time and cover your own costs for travel, etc., but EHDEN covers the full cost of the programme so that you can be up and running as soon as possible.

- **Open source community boosts opportunities**

EHDEN is deeply connected with the OHDSI worldwide initiative, which gathers a very active open source community that is continuously developing and improving software tools for better data analysis and use. By participating in EHDEN, SMEs interested in software tools will be able to contribute to this dynamic community, share the burden of development and validation, build services on top of such tools and benefit from the many opportunities that a worldwide, ever growing peer community offers to boost adoption and exploitation of the OMOP CDM.

- **Thriving community facilitates hands-on training of new staff**

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Besides tool and service development, the OHDSI and EHDEN communities conform a perfect space for hands-on training of personnel, facilitating expertise acquisition, a fast learning curve and continuing career development in a way that no SME could afford internally by itself.

- **Synergic ecosystem facilitates exposure and brand recognition with key stakeholders**

EHDEN will gather many different types of stakeholders: hospitals and other data custodians, pharmaceutical companies, regulatory and health technology assessment agencies, healthcare authorities, software developers, patient representatives, ... Participating in EHDEN will immediately help your company to be exposed to such a variety of institutions in Europe and, through OHDSI, worldwide, in the context of a collaborative environment, facilitating contacts with different types of potential customers and allies, helping market positioning and brand recognition in a much faster way than any marketing or outreach campaign would be able to achieve.

4.2. Value propositions for Data sources/Data custodians/National Health Data Networks (Data Partners)

4.2.1. Objectives of outreach

- To raise **awareness of the value of real-world evidence**, the current challenges of generating evidence from existing source data
- To highlight how the **OMOP CDM as a data standard** and **OHDSI tools as an analytics standard** can improve the efficiency, quality, and reproducibility of the real-world evidence generation process.
- To raise awareness on the **existing procedures and support** to apply open community data standards (OMOP CDM) to your health data.
- To raise **awareness on the benefits of belonging to the community**, including **available tools**.
- To get commitment to participate in the EHDEN community.
- To sound out interest in participating in studies.
- To raise **awareness on EHDEN and EHDEN grants**.

4.2.2. Key concepts for VP

Headline:

Option 1: “Let your data speak to the world”

Option 2: “Add value to your data to create evidence”

Option 3: “Help your data create evidence. Let your evidence help the world”

Key benefits

1. Facilitates **scientific collaboration**, facilitates the connections with peers and learnings by becoming part of a thriving **academic/medical network and community**. Participate in an eco-system with multiple data partners, data users and key stakeholders, including HTA and regulatory agencies.
2. Boost **opportunities to participate** in international studies for larger academic impact.
3. Improved **interoperability**. Expand the value of your data by enabling its re-use across a wide range of analytic use cases, including clinical characterization for disease natural history and quality improvement, population-level effect estimation for safety surveillance and comparative effectiveness, and patient-level prediction for disease interception and precision medicine.
4. **Financial support** for uptake, extension and validation of mappings (**EHDEN grants**).

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5. Increased **visibility** for your data, expanding opportunities to be approached for sponsored studies helping long term sustainability of the data source with stable revenue streams.
6. Increased capability for **analysis** thanks to a host of **open source tools** to use. Quickly and **consistently design** and perform studies (cohort definition, etc.).
7. Increased **transparency** of analyses and **reproducibility**, enabling studies to be easily ‘transposed’ to other data sources for multiplied impact (e.g. in publications).
8. **Faster** performing studies, improved performance, accelerated research (months/years to days): undertake **more studies in less time, with less resources**
9. **Assurance** of scientific independence, freedom to perform studies, respect own approval procedures.
10. Support **own decision-making processes**, potential to propagate learnings to increase compliance and improvement in underlying healthcare systems. Added possibilities for **auditing/refining/visualising your own data** – KNOW your data, revealing the potential flaws for continued improvement. **Integrative analysis** of own multiple databases.
11. Platform for **training** of young researchers and new staff, not least through the EHDEN Academy.
12. Framework to **demonstrate reliability and utility of observational data** analyses.
13. Need to get ready for a new research environment and evidence generation framework worldwide.

4.2.3. VP team members

The members for this VP team are:

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4.2.4. VP full text

The following text develops the key benefits in section 4.2.2 above. This will serve as guideline to develop argumentation for outreach teams contacting potentially interested data partners, and as text that can be directly used for dissemination materials, web site, etc.

HELP YOUR DATA CREATE EVIDENCE. LET YOUR EVIDENCE HELP THE WORLD.

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- Easier scientific collaboration through a thriving community**

Having your data mapped to a common data model (CDM) and becoming an EHDEN Data Partner facilitates connections and collaboration with hundreds of peers and exchange of learnings on an unprecedented scale. Methods can be seamlessly shared and results can more easily be integrated across sources, regions and countries securely. Becoming a Data Partner in EHDEN also means that you can contribute and benefit from an ever-expanding network of researchers and data scientists from all kinds of institutions, including key stakeholders such as HTA and regulatory agencies. A vibrant academic and medical research community awaits you.
- Boost opportunities to participate in international studies for larger impact**

The much larger conclusive power of the evidence that can be generated through the EHDEN eco-system will be attractive for everyone. This will mean that your opportunities to participate in large international networks and studies, that may appear as otherwise not accessible now, will be multiplied, as will the impact of any research results derived from such studies. You will also be able to initiate studies yourself so that your own research is amplified and benefits from many other OMOP-mapped datasets of peer Data Partners interested in the same questions.
- Improved interoperability adds value to your data**

Common data models such as OMOP are all about interoperability – the capability of systems to speak a common language and understand each other. Mapping to OMOP allows datasets to contribute to generating evidence on a much larger scale. By participating in EHDEN, you expand the value of your data by enabling its re-use across a wide range of analytic use cases, including clinical characterization for disease natural history and quality improvement, population-level effect estimation for safety surveillance and comparative effectiveness, or patient-level prediction for disease interception and precision medicine.
- Financial support for uptake, extension and validation of mappings**

EHDEN will periodically launch calls for potential Data Partners that want to adopt the OMOP CDM, through which funding will be directly granted. This may be an exceptional opportunity to jump the bandwagon and reap the benefits of mapping your datasets to a common data model at minimal or no cost. It is foreseen that three types of calls will be launched: a) for mapping data to the OMOP CDM; b) for extending the mapping, in case it has already been tackled; and c) to validate the mapping, if already done. Data Partners receiving funding will be able to use it to hire one of the EHDEN-certified small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) to do the mapping for them.
- Increased visibility for your capacity**

Belonging to the EHDEN eco-system and having your datasets mapped to OMOP CDM will expose your potential to a world of opportunities. You could be approached for sponsored academic studies, trial recruitment, regulatory studies, collaborative European projects... Whether you are very active already in collaborative initiatives, or just starting to be known, your research capacity will be promoted, potential boosted and network multiplied. These opportunities may help realise the value of your data and secure the financial sustainability of your data source with stable revenue streams.
- Enhanced capability for study design and analysis thanks to a host of open source tools**

Once your data is mapped to the OMOP CDM, you get access to many open source tools developed by the OHDSI community. These tools will allow you to quickly and consistently design and perform studies, visualise and analyse data. These tools are free and easy to use, and the OHDSI and EHDEN communities include educational resources to learn how to use them and maximise their usefulness in a variety of settings. An EHDEN Academy has been set up to gather and organise educational resources underpinning the eco-system, which will make things even easier.
- Increased reproducibility and transparency of analyses**

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One of the many advantages of mapping to the OMOP CDM is the fact that methods and analyses can be more easily applied to many data sets for a much larger impact. This increases transparency towards the research and open science community and facilitates reproducibility of studies across diverse settings, increasing the opportunities for rapid learning across the EHDEN eco-system, and boosting the value and confidence in the evidence it generates.

- **Faster performing studies for accelerated research**

Good research takes time. But the world moves fast nowadays, and human and financial resources are scarce. Efficiency is critical for the survival of any organisation, and this has to be achieved without sacrificing quality. Having your data mapped to OMOP CDM means that some analyses can take days instead of months or years, and still use all best practice to generate reliable evidence. This means that you can undertake more studies in less time, decide quicker on whether a research question is futile, explore sensitivity analyses much more efficiently and, in conclusion, be able to generate evidence at a much higher rate – so that any new insight can reach the patient as soon as possible.

- **Federated approach allows to retain full control of the data**

By supporting a federated approach to the undertaking of studies, EHDEN ensures that data custodians retain control of their data at all times. Scientific independence will not in any way be compromised, nor will your local governance rules, regulations and approval procedures. Your freedom is completely preserved: you still decide in which studies you participate, and you can participate in other networks or projects at your will – no exclusivity is required. You can maintain your current academic and/or commercial interests. The EHDEN eco-system just offers you a lot of additional opportunities – but the final call is always yours.

- **Support your own decision-making processes by easily characterising and visualising your data**

You know your data. But experience shows that the process of mapping them to a common data model and being able to use them at large can have enormous benefits within your own organisation alone. You will be able to use the OHDSI and EHDEN tools on your dataset, visualise your data in many ways, characterise them, refine coding practices, propagate learnings in your organisation and downstream. In healthcare systems, where strategic decision making heavily depends on reliable data, it may be invaluable to gain real-time insight more rapidly and inexpensively. If you have multiple datasets, you will be able to manage aggregated views, and analyse them in several ways. You will simply get more out of your own data for your own needs.

- **Platform for training of young researchers and new staff**

Being part of an active community means that new staff and early career researchers will have numerous ways to learn, quickly and effectively, the skills needed to work with both data mapped to OMOP CDM and open source tools. This in fact creates a rapid learning environment that alleviates the cost of personnel turnover and makes it easier to preserve the knowledge acquired through the undertaking of studies – so that such knowledge can be consulted and re-used in the future.

- **Framework to demonstrate reliability and utility of observational data analyses**

For anyone whose research or professional interests are related with the use of observational data, it is important to demonstrate the value of such data, especially in the context of practical real-life scenarios. The eco-system that EHDEN is building aims to help prove the reliability and utility of observational data analyses to generate real-world evidence – and, the more proven this is, the more value observational data will have for all kinds of stakeholders.

- **Improve your readiness for a new research environment and evidence generation framework**

The advent of new environments where rapid evidence generation at scale is required for decision making, be it in healthcare, regulatory, drug development or even in academic settings, is not the distant future. It is here already. Preparing your data for such a connected new world will be the safest way to

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make sure that data, and the knowledge that it contains, continues to be generated, collected and used for the global benefit of citizens worldwide. Help your data create evidence. Let your evidence help the world.

4.3. Value propositions for Regulatory/Health Technology Assessment/Payer agencies

4.3.1. Objectives of outreach

- To **understand the needs**, requirements and expectations of these agencies in terms of data (access, quality, analysis).
- To understand the **methods/value frameworks** of these agencies.
- To raise **awareness on OMOP-CDM** as enabler of standardised analytics yielding real-world evidence.
- To raise **awareness on EHDEN**.
- To identify **early adopters**: HTA/Regulatory agencies that spearhead innovation in the field. Identify big players and opinion leaders that can create a snowball effect in the field.
- To identify **champions** that would act as advocates for EHDEN within their institutions.
- To create a **collaborative framework** with EHDEN.

4.3.2. Key concepts for VP

Headline: “**GET RELEVANT REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE FASTER**”

1. Increased **transparency, robustness and reliability** of data processing supporting decision-making
2. Support **own decision-making** processes
3. Easier assessment of **data quality**. Active participation in the community and interaction with data sources may allow these agencies to **influence** the generation of data with the outcomes necessary for their decision making: increased “**fit for purposeness**”
4. **Increased capability for analysis**, real-time surveillance (e.g. dashboards). A host of **open source tools** to use on own databases
5. Increased capacity to look at patients holistically across health systems
6. Effective use of (limited) resources
7. Increased capacity to perform **international studies** or **regional studies** (especially important in Europe)
8. Increased capacity to carry out studies with big geographical coverage
9. Potential for improved **disease understanding** and support to learning healthcare systems
10. **Faster** performance of studies, accelerated research (months/years to days)
11. Quickly and **consistently design** studies (cohort definition, etc.) Facilitate research **reproducibility enabling networks of sources to replicate results**
12. Framework to demonstrate reliability and utility of observational data analyses
13. **Sharing best practice** with other agencies for better integration and consistency across Europe
14. Need to get ready for a new environment (“21st century research”)

4.3.3. VP team members

The members for this VP team are:

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4.3.4. VP full text

The following text develops the key benefits in section 4.3.2 above. This will serve as guideline to develop argumentation for outreach teams contacting potentially interested regulatory/HTA/payer agencies, and as text that can be directly used for dissemination materials, web site, etc.

GET RELEVANT REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE FASTER

- Increased transparency, robustness and reliability of data processing**
 Real-world data can help better understand disease processes, interventions, the impact of regulatory decisions, and changes in clinical practice. However, real-world data are usually complex, noisy, heterogeneous and scattered across institutions. A common data model implemented across many data sources allows the transparent use of common methods and tools. They can be used to process data robustly so that the reliability of evidence can be assessed better, and studies can be more easily reproduced in diverse settings.
- Support own decision-making processes**
 The EHDEN ecosystem aims to create an environment where evidence can be generated from the ever-growing amounts of health data more quickly. HTA bodies, payers, and regulatory agencies will benefit from better access to data and the tools to analyse them to support their decision-making processes. For example, by verifying the claims made by pharmaceutical, biotech or medical device companies in bigger and richer datasets. EHDEN could also help to gain better insights into rare disease or neglected diseases. Furthermore, once a data source or research method has been deemed fit for HTA decision making, applicants (e.g. pharma, biotech companies) could be asked to use these data or methods to produce the evidence they submit to different agencies.
- Easier assessment of data quality and “fit-for-purposeness” of data**
 Real-world data are typically collected for a purpose. Data collected to document clinical care may be very different at a fundamental level from those collected for research or managerial purposes. When confronted with a question, we run the risk of trying to get an answer using data sets that were not gathered for that type of purpose. A quality framework and common data characterisation may help avoid such situations. A wide implementation of the OMOP CDM will allow easier assessment of quality of the underlying data on all ‘traditional’ dimensions (completeness, accuracy, consistency, etc.), a topic that is still a priority as acknowledged by international initiatives such as EUnetHTA, GetReal or ADAPT-

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SMART. But, perhaps more importantly, it can help to evaluate whether the used data are appropriate for the question posed in the first place. Moreover, regulatory agencies, HTA bodies, and payers can influence the generation of the evidence they need through active participation in a thriving research community and interaction with data sources. For example, they can incentivise the measurement of outcomes they prefer. A virtuous circle can therefore be enabled: the more data are used, the more studies are implemented using transparent methods and analytics, the greater the drive will be towards improving quality and “fit-for-purposeness” of data.

- **Increased capability for analysis through open source tools**

One of the great advantages of the OMOP CDM is the host of open source tools that are continuously developed and maintained by the OHDSI community, and to which EHDEN will decisively contribute. These include tools for data analysis, visualisation and real-time surveillance (e.g. dashboards), and also include extensive tutorials and community support. Tools and methods can be consistently implemented on any data source mapped to the OMOP common data model, including data sources available in house at the different agencies.

- **Increased capacity to look at patients holistically across health institutions**

Widespread implementation of a common data model also helps linkage in order to be able to follow patients in their healthcare journey across institutions and even jurisdictions, for holistic views that are rarely possible nowadays, and that could shed new light on disease processes, and the potential impact of specific measures that are proposed by authorities.

- **More effective use of limited resources**

Many public and academic organisations have limited resources. As a result, efficient use of resources is important to them and EHDEN can contribute to this by helping set up relationships with hundreds of data custodians, analytics experts and method developers much more efficiently thanks to the creation of a shared collaborative space.

- **Increased capacity to perform international studies or regional studies**

Answers to questions by regulatory agencies increasingly require international studies to be carried out, especially in the case of Europe with many different national/regional health systems, cultures, practices and great diversity in data collection and availability. Analyses needed to support decision-making often need to be run across multiple data sources, so methods must be able to be consistently applied (requiring data and analysis standards) and evidence needs to be able to be directly synthesized, documented and reproduced if needed. Confidence in results is greatly enhanced if consistent findings across independent sources can be produced. The ambition of EHDEN is to encompass all kinds of data sources throughout Europe. This also means that national and regional agencies can consistently be able to generate studies using data from its own jurisdiction, which will be highly relevant for HTAs.

- **Increased capacity to carry out studies with big geographical coverage**

The close links of EHDEN with the OHDSI community will facilitate network studies across continents, for European data to be compared with North America and Asia-Pacific data. This could have value to regulators who want to know if observed patterns in their jurisdiction are similar to other areas outside their jurisdiction. Treatment pathways studies may identify unique patterns in one country that aren't detected anywhere else, or they may reveal unexpected similarities. Impact on risk avoidance measures could be studied on many levels. Effects of alternative policies and interventions could be researched across different health systems and evidence-based decision making on questions that depend on real-world data will be greatly facilitated.

- **Potential for improved disease understanding and support to learning healthcare systems**

Beyond key decision-making procedures, active intervention of regulatory and HTA agencies in EHDEN will keep public interest at the top of the agenda of the ecosystem. Efforts to improve disease

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understanding, better data generation, improved methods and analytics have to not lose focus on the ultimate beneficiary: the patient. With the expected increase in generation of patient-reported outcomes in the next years, standardisation and harmonisation of data will be of even greater importance – and EHDEN can contribute decisively to the development of learning healthcare systems that are able to dynamically and continuously feed from growing data and knowledge to help provide the best care for everyone at the right time.

- **Faster performance of studies**

In order to serve the need for faster evidence generation in the framework of reducing the time and resources required for the development and assessment of new therapies and interventions, research has to be conducted faster without compromising quality. Timely decisions are required to cope with expectations as research advances, while ensuring that risks are adequately controlled. Having a catalogue of well characterized datasets will reduce the time for selection and assessment of data relevant for research. Furthermore, having a plethora of data sets mapped to OMOP CDM means that some analyses can take days instead of months or years, and still use all best practice to generate reliable evidence. This means that you can undertake more studies in less time, decide quicker on whether a research question is futile, explore sensitivity analyses much more efficiently and, in conclusion, be able to generate evidence at a much higher rate – so that any new and potentially life-changing insight can reach the patient as soon as possible.

- **Facilitate research reproducibility**

One of the many advantages of mapping to the OMOP CDM is the fact that methods, analyses and studies can be consistently designed and more easily applied to, and replicated on, many data sets for a much larger impact. This increases transparency towards the research and open science community and facilitates reproducibility of studies across diverse settings, increasing the opportunities for rapid learning across the EHDEN eco-system, and boosting the value and confidence in the evidence it generates.

- **Framework to demonstrate reliability and utility of observational data analyses**

For anyone whose research or professional interests are related with the use of observational data, it is important to demonstrate the value of such data, especially in the context of practical real-life scenarios. The eco-system that EHDEN is building aims to help prove the reliability and utility of observational data analyses to generate real-world evidence – and, the more proven this is, the more value observational data will have for all kinds of stakeholders.

- **Sharing best practice with other agencies**

Specifically in the regulatory/HTA/payer environment, agencies frameworks can significantly differ among jurisdictions. The EHDEN ecosystem can represent a shared platform for exchange of experiences and best practice in the use of real-world data, helping better integration and consistency across Europe.

- **Increased preparedness for future research environments**

The advent of new environments where rapid evidence generation at scale is required for decision making, be it in healthcare, regulatory, drug development or even in academic settings, is not the distant future. It is here already. Preparing for such a connected new world will be the safest way to make sure that data, and the potential knowledge that it contains, continues to be generated, collected and used for the global benefit of citizens worldwide. The EHDEN platform has been designed as a self-sustaining, ever-growing community that will contribute to the ultimate goal to share and develop standards for evidence generation in parallel to new ways of understanding patients needs. That way, it could be your benchmark platform for assessment of any new methodologies and ways to understand patients, diseases and therapies.

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5. NEXT STEPS

Within WP6, it has been agreed to continue the work on the Value Propositions addressing additional stakeholder groups. WP6 team members have agreed to focus on pharmaceutical industry and patients/patient representatives as the next stakeholders for which VPs will be developed.

In addition, the text on the Value Propositions included above will be continuously refined using the feedback received from anyone having used its content, aiming at progressively refining the text on the basis of actual experience.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1 – Online survey for Stakeholder groups

Survey 1: SMEs

Questionnaire on
Value Proposition fc

Survey 2: Data sources/Data custodians/National Health Data Networks (Data Partners)

Questionnaire on
Value Proposition fc

Survey 3: Regulatory/Health Technology Assessment/Payer agencies

Questionnaire on
Value Proposition fc